

CHORSU MARKET" AND NATIONAL FOOD AND NATIONAL POTTERY

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Abstract

This article covers the famous ceramic products of Chorsu market, national costumes, national Uzbek dishes (food market) and everything that is interesting for us and tourists. During the writing of the article, I interviewed many people. I also interviewed sellers and shop owners who have been operating at Chorsu market for many years; I also interviewed ceramic products made by hand. Finally, I visited the Food Market, the busiest place in Chorsu, and interviewed the chefs and customers there.

Keywords: *national, costumes, dishes, handicrafts, ceramic products.*

Every time I visit Chorsu Bazaar, I walk past the Mosque and I will briefly tell you about entering from this place. This beautiful Mosque is the Khoja Ahrar Vali Mosque, which is an architectural monument. The appearance of the Mosque is in the architectural style of the Uzbek national architecture of Islam and the Middle East. The total area is 0.20 hectares, the size is 90x35, and the number of domes is 3. Marble and brick were used in the construction of the Mosque. Currently, the last imam of the Mosque is Maqsudali Qosimov. This Mosque mainly serves the merchants of Chorsu Bazaar and can accommodate more than 2,000 worshipers. To enter Chorsu Bazaar, I walk along the stairs next to the Mosque.

We can find many bookstores in the row of the Khoja Ahrar Vali Mosque. You can find and buy all kinds of books in these bookstores. I personally like this type of books, so I took photos of them. You can also find out what kind of book it is from its cover, that is, from the title, such books can attract a person's attention at first glance. Reading each book, you will have new thoughts and conclusions, especially if these books are written in a realistic interpretation....

We started the next step with delicacies, that is, we came to the food stalls of the Chorsu market. The stalls are located on the middle and upper floors and are divided according to the type of goods sold: fruits, vegetables, oriental sweets, spices, grains. Pavilions are allocated in other areas for deer meat and household goods.

Each pavilion will leave you with a unique impression, which is why a sense of nationality is felt at every step. The sweet attitude and open faces of the sellers will not leave anyone indifferent. The most exquisite and affordable products will encourage you to buy more. Where else can you find such a beautiful sight?

If we move on to our next stall, we will see such beautiful and unique handicrafts. It is here that you can see our nationality, unique handicrafts that are unparalleled and can arouse interest in many people. Each item is decorated with unique beautiful and unique patterns. Basically, in this photo, ceramic items are treated with colors. You can see: ceramic plates of various sizes, bowls, cups, musical instruments, and even old grandfather-shaped vases that will add beauty to your home.

Moving on to our next row, we will see such beautiful and unique handicrafts. It is here that you can see our nationality, unique handicrafts that are unparalleled and can arouse interest in many people. Each item is decorated with beautiful and unique patterns. Basically, in this picture, ceramic items are treated with colors. Please see: you can also find ceramic

plates of various sizes, bowls, cups, musical instruments, and old grandfather-shaped dishes that will add beauty to your home. If you pay attention to the bottom row, you can see dishes (plates) with images of regions. Nationality and labor are reflected in every detail. It is clear that the craftsman had to work hard to make these handiwork reach the hearts of people.

Continuing on the road, we met Hakimjonov Sirojiddin near the gold shops and continued our conversation. First, they introduced themselves, saying that they have been working at the Chorsu market for 2 years. They said that they talk to many people and that they like their work. One by one, they introduced them to handicrafts. What caught my attention was the way Sirojiddin greeted customers in a national way. Here is our real Uzbek boy.

The next hardworking person we met was Yuldashov Hassan. He is a cheerful and humorous person, and his colleagues also noted his habits. He said that he has been working here for many years and feeding his family, and thank God, we are no less than anyone else. What difficulties do you encounter in the process of preparing food? When a person is busy with his favorite profession, there are no difficulties, but fatigue is a natural state, he said. My head hurts a little because the market is crowded with people, but I forget quickly when I am busy with work.

The turn has come for the most famous dish of the Chorsu food market, namely Khanim. The Uzbek woman you see in the photo is Nazarov Farida opa.

I have known them for almost a year, and no one can prepare Khanim with such special love as they do. There is probably no one who has not tasted this doughy dish, but Chorsu Khanim is completely unique. It intoxicates anyone with its appearance and smell.

I will see you at the Chorsu metro station

I think this article was useful to you and us.